

Numerical analysis of wave overtopping of rubble mound breakwaters

Inigo J. Losada, Javier L. Lara, Raul Guanche and Jose M. Gonzalez-Ondina

Ocean & Coastal Research Group

University of Cantabria

E.T.S.I. de Caminos, Canales y Puertos. Avda. de los Castros s/n. 39005 Santander. Spain.

Corresponding author: losadai@unican.es

Abstract

The paper describes the results of a two-dimensional (2-D) numerical modelling investigation of the functionality of rubble mound breakwaters with special attention focused on wave overtopping processes. The model, COBRAS-UC, is a new version of the COBRAS (Cornell Breaking Waves and Structures) based on the Volume Averaged Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes (VARANS) equations and uses a Volume of Fluid Technique (VOF) method to capture the free surface. The nature of the model equations and solving technique provides a means to simulate wave reflection, run-up, wave breaking on the slope, transmission through rubble mounds, overtopping and agitation at the protected side due to the combined effect of wave transmission and overtopping. Also, two-dimensional experimental studies are carried out to investigate the performance of the model. The computations of the free surface and pressure time series and spectra under regular and irregular waves, are compared with the experimental data reaching a very good agreement. The model is also used to reproduce instantaneous and average wave overtopping discharge. Comparisons with existing semi-empirical formulae and experimental data show a very good performance. The present model is expected to become in the near future an excellent tool for practical applications.

Keywords: Rubble-mound breakwater; RANS modelling; wave transformation; overtopping, functional design; numerical modelling.

1. Introduction

Wave overtopping of coastal structures is one of the most relevant processes taking part in the complex water wave and structure interaction phenomenon. Once the highest run-up levels exceed the structure crown, overtopping occurs, which may cause structural failure, damage to harbor infrastructures, properties and lives. Research on wave overtopping has been of great interest during the last decades. Very important developments have been achieved during the last years thanks to several European projects (f.i. CLASH and VOWS). The prediction of wave overtopping is especially challenging since it involves complicated processes such as wave run-up on permeable or impermeable slopes, wave breaking and associated turbulence; wave infiltration and transmission in rubble mound layers or violent impacts on monolithic walls. In general, most of the existing research has been directed towards the evaluation of the mean overtopping discharge. However, this may not be the fundamental parameter. Therefore, further efforts have been oriented towards the evaluation of other important parameters such as the volume of the maximum individual overtopping event or overtopping probability. Furthermore, the thickness of the overtopping layer and the associated flow velocity; the evaluation of forces on the structure during an overtopping event; the forces induced on infrastructures, vehicles or people on the crown of the structure or the transmission leeward the structure induced by overtopping events are also of great interest. The main problem is that overtopping depends on structure typology, geometry, material characteristics, incident wave conditions and foreshore bathymetry requiring a strong parameterization to include all the relevant elements.

In order to provide design guidelines for coastal structures many semi-empirical formulations based on flume and basin experiments have been developed in the past. Such formulae try to consider and parameterize the most relevant variables ruling the

process. Most of them are simple expressions describing mean overtopping discharges and are biased towards sloping or vertical seawalls, for example Owen (1980), van der Meer et al. (1995), Hedges and Reis (1998) and Besley (1999). Formulae for rubble mound structures are also available in literature, Franco (1994) and Franco and Franco (1999), Allsop et al. (1985), later improved by Besley (1999), and Pedersen (1996).

Some efforts have focused on the empirical prediction of the volume of maximum overtopping events, Owen (1980) and Franco et al. (1994) as an important criterion for design. Most of the formulae are summarized in Burcharth and Hughes (2006) and will be included in the forthcoming “European Wave Overtopping Manual”.

These empirical formulations have been the main tool for coastal structures design and have proved to be successful. However, they are based on flume or wave basin experiments covering a limited number of typologies and setups. Furthermore, many of them are based on a reduced set of incident wave conditions including mostly regular waves or narrow-banded spectra. Their use out of range, a problem often faced for design, may require extrapolations increasing uncertainties, and/or lead to important errors. To overcome these limitations computational modeling of wave interaction with coastal structures has grown as a serious complementary approach during the last decade, Losada (2003).

Numerical model performance for wave and structure interaction including wave overtopping, depends on the equations and solving technique and rely heavily on a thorough validation process. The most popular models are based on different forms of the nonlinear shallow water equations (NSWE), f.e. Kobayashi and Wurjanto (1989), Mingham and Causson (1998), Hu et al. (2000), Hubbard and Dodd (2002), Stansby and Feng (2004). The NSWE are derived on the assumption of hydrostatic pressure and are

obtained by vertically integrating the Navier-Stokes equations. Models based on these equations are very efficient providing the chance to simulate wave trains including about 1000 waves very rapidly, which may be of importance to analyze extreme statistics of wave overtopping. However, the use of NSWE places severe restrictions to real applications inherent to the hypothesis behind their derivation. One restriction is that the offshore boundary condition of the numerical model has to be located close to the structure in order to satisfy the shallow water limit. This restriction is especially crude when considering high frequency components in the incident wave spectrum. This may lead to important errors in the estimation of wave overtopping. Additional restrictions are associated with the semi-empirical introduction of breaking, porous flow modeling or the difficulty in simulating complicated free surfaces.

A second and more recent alternative is the use of particle methods like the Moving Particle Semi-Implicit (MPS) method of Koshizuka et al. (1995); or the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method in its different versions (f.e. Dalrymple et al (2001), Gotoh et al. (2004) and Shao et al. (2006)). The main advantage of these models, being a grid-less Lagrangian approach, is that they provide excellent capability to track large deformations of the free surface with good accuracy. However, SPH models are, at the moment, only applicable to impermeable structures and have a clear disadvantage compared to other models, their extremely low computational efficiency. As a consequence, limited validation but promising initial results are currently available (i.e. Shao et al., 2006).

A third alternative is the numerical model based on the Navier-Stokes equations. The main advantage of these models is that they overcome the limitations associated with using a given wave theory and include wave breaking thanks to incorporating a turbulence model and considering Reynolds Average (RANS) equations. Those

including a Volume of Fluid technique to track the free surface are becoming very powerful since they are able to consider large free surface deformations. Moreover, they are computationally more efficient than the SPH models. Several researchers have been working on this type of models (f.e.: Troch and de Rouck, 1998; Kawasaki, 1999; Li et al., 2004).

Liu et al. (1999) presented a RANS model, nicknamed COBRAS (Cornell Breaking Waves and Structures) for simulating breaking waves overtopping a porous structure. The model calculated the mean flow in the fluid region based on the Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations, the corresponding turbulence field being modelled by an improved $k-\varepsilon$ model. The flow in porous structures was described by the spatially averaged Navier-Stokes equations. However, due to model and computational limitations the model was validated for a vertical caisson protected by an armoured layer made of tetrapods in a very small computational domain (7.348 m x 0.43 m) and for a very short simulation time ($t=18.2$ s) and therefore for a limited number of regular waves (13).

In a second paper Hsu et al. (2002) extended the original COBRAS model, introducing the Volume-Averaged/Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (VARANS) equations to describe surface wave interaction with coastal structures. In the VARANS equations, the volume-averaged Reynolds stress is modelled by adopting the nonlinear eddy viscosity assumption and the volume-averaged turbulent kinetic energy and its dissipation rate are derived by taking the volume-average of the standard $k-\varepsilon$ equations. This model has the advantage of introducing the small-scale turbulence effects as part of the porous flow. Validation is carried out using the experimental set in Liu et al. (1999) and is also for a very small domain and limited simulation time. In this case, most of the validation focuses on the regular wave field in front of the structure.

In this paper an improved version of COBRAS, COBRAS-UC, developed at the University of Cantabria is used to investigate the interaction of random waves with rubble mound breakwaters focusing on the complicated overtopping process. The model is used to simulate a large numerical wave flume including random waves and long simulation times, which may contribute to reduce some uncertainties in using semi-empirical formulae for design and provide some statistical information on the overtopping process.

The paper is organized in the following manner. The main modifications introduced in the initial COBRAS version are presented in the following section. Section 3 describes the physical model experimental work carried out for model validation, including free surface, pressure and wave overtopping measurements in a rubble mound breakwater under regular and irregular wave conditions. Section 4 is devoted to the explanation of the numerical setup and model calibration. Model capabilities to simulate wave overtopping are shown in section 5. Comparisons between measured and numerically calculated average overtopping discharge, percentage (probability) of overtopping waves and maximum individual overtopping volume are presented. Finally, in section 6, some practical implications of this work are considered and conclusions are drawn.

2. Description of COBRAS-UC numerical model

By taking the volume-average of RANS equations, Liu et al. (1999) presented a two-dimensional numerical model to describe the flow inside and outside coastal structures including permeable layers. Hsu et al. (2002) extended the preliminary model by including a set of volume-averaged k - ε turbulence balance equations employed to calculate the turbulent kinetic energy (k) and the turbulence damping rate (ε). The volume-averaged stress and volume-averaged strain rate are nonlinearly related through

an eddy viscosity closure model. In the numerical model, the two-step projection method is employed to solve the VARANS equations. The movement of free surface is tracked by the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method. That means that, initially, Hsu et al. (2002) can be considered as one of the most advanced models able to address most of the processes involved in the complex wave and structure interaction problem, including turbulence inside the permeable structures.

In the VARANS equations, the interfacial forces between the fluids and solids have been modeled by the extended Forchheimer relationship, in which both linear and nonlinear drag forces are included. Two empirical coefficients, α and β , respectively associated with the linear and nonlinear forces, are introduced. These coefficients should depend on the Reynolds number and flow direction. An inertia term is also included in the extended Forchheimer equation. Detailed discussions on the numerical algorithms, initial and boundary conditions can be found in Lin and Liu (1998a) and Hsu *et al.* (2002).

Even though the initial validations described in the aforementioned works have shown excellent and promising results, the initial code required extensive additional modifications to carry out a detailed validation and to make it useful for engineering applications.

Therefore, a number of modifications have been introduced into the original COBRAS code at the University of Cantabria in order to overcome some of the initial limitations and especially to convert it into a tool for practical application. Most of these modifications in the new version COBRAS-UC, have been founded on the extensive validation work carried out for low-crested structures (Garcia et al. 2004, Losada et al. 2005 and Lara et al. 2006a) and wave breaking on permeable slopes (Lara et al. 2006b) carried out with the model. The improvements cover the wave generation process; code updating and refactoring; optimization and improvement of the main subroutines;

improvement of input and output data definition and the development of a graphical user interface and output data processing programs. Regarding wave generation a set of pre-processing tools have been developed to define target regular and irregular wave conditions based on either theoretical formulations, laboratory or field information. Irregular wave generation has been implemented considering TMA and JONSWAP-type input spectra as well as wave groups with a free number of components. Optionally, sponge layers can be defined in any region of the domain to absorb wave propagating offshore the generation region.

Regarding code updating and refactoring, most of the initial COBRAS code is directly based on the RIPPLE code (Kothe et al., 1991) strongly modified and extended by several researchers from multiple institutions resulting in a complex and cryptic structure making it difficult to find problems in the code. Consequently the initial code has been converted to FORTRAN 90 and most of the code has been rewritten and compiled to run on standard PCs. Regarding optimization and improvement of the subroutines, one of the main subroutines in RIPPLE is devoted to the resolution of the Poisson pressure equation. This subroutine has been modified and the iterative process used to solve the matrix improved, resulting in a remarkable reduction in the number of iterations.

One of the major limitations in the use of COBRAS as an operative engineering tool lay on the mesh generation process and definition of the elements of the flume or prototype to be modeled (solid obstacles, porous media, etc.). The obstacles and porous media were defined with a series of conic sections that might overlap one another to form arbitrarily complex boundaries and whose equations were to be defined and introduced by the user, resulting in an extremely tedious task for large and complicated structures. Furthermore, this method could give rise to problems on the border between obstacles,

where a false fluid area might be generated. In order to overcome these problems a graphical user interface has been created to define the initial parameters necessary for the simulation including the generation of elements with irregular shapes to describe the structures. The interface includes a new technique to generate obstacles which makes it more simple and avoids previously detected sources of errors.

With the aforementioned modifications being implemented, the computational cost of the model has been reduced by 40 % compared to the initial code for a typical run. Several execution problems have been eliminated and the memory requirements reduced opening the possibility to consider larger and more complex computational domains and longer simulation times. COBRAS-UC opens the possibility to a more extensive and thorough validation process, as well as to the application of the model to large and prototype scales; due to the production of reliable statistical information in the short term.

3. Description of the experiments

In order to evaluate the model's capability to simulate wave overtopping, a set of experiments on wave interaction with a rubble mound breakwater was carried out in the wave flume of the University of Cantabria. The flume is 60.5 m long, 2 m wide and 2 m high. At one side of the wave flume, a mixed piston-pendulum type wave maker has two attached free surface wave gauges integrated in an Active Wave Absorption System (AWACS®) that allows the absorption of reflected waves. At the rear end of the wave flume, three dissipative ramps were placed to absorb the transmitted waves.

The breakwater, see Figure 1, is built of an impermeable caisson installed on a rubble mound foundation. The impermeable caisson is 1.04 m long, 0.3 m high and 2 m wide. The still water level was 0.8 m and the structure freeboard was 0.2 m. A 0.7 m high, D_{50}

= 0.01 cm and $1V/2H$ gravel core was placed below the breakwater. The core was covered with three external layers; two of them were gravel with $D_{50} = 3.5$ cm and one external layer of gravel with $D_{50} = 13.5$ cm. At the seaside face of the structure, a 14 cm berm was built. The porosity was 0.48 for the core and 0.50 for the outer layers. A reservoir was built at the crown of the structure in order to collect the water which overtops the structure. The top of the reservoir was aligned with the upper face of the caisson so as not to generate interference with the flow. The box only occupied a third of the width of the wave flume, allowing most of the overtopped flow to reach the leeward side of the structure.

Figure 1. Breakwater geometry (dimension in meters)

3.1. Instrumentation

Free surface evolution was measured using resistive wave gauges (WG) located along the flume. The gauges were placed in three different regions: seaward and leeward the caisson and on the top of the caisson. Along the centreline of the wave flume, 10 wave gauges were located in front of the vertical breakwater. Three of them were used to evaluate the reflection coefficient. Three wave gauges were placed on the top of the caisson to measure the thickness of the water layer during the overtopping events. One wave gauge was placed at the leeward side of the structure. Finally, the overtopping discharge was evaluated by measuring the water volume jumps in the reservoir of each overtopping wave. The water depth multiplied by the horizontal area of the reservoir (0.69 m^2) gives the instantaneous volume of water inside the box. A resistive wave gauge placed inside the pool recorded the free surface variation in the reservoir.

A total of ten pressure transducers, six at the front wall and four underneath, were installed to measure pressure distribution around the caisson. The pressure transducers (PG) underneath the caisson are also an excellent means to evaluate how wave energy is transmitted through the gravel core. In Figure 2 a sketch of the experimental set-up is shown. The sampling frequency was 60 Hz.

Figure 2. Instrumentation set-up. Pressure gauges (PG) and free surface gauges (WG).

3.2. Experimental Wave Conditions

Regular and random waves were considered in the experiments. Fifth-order Stokes waves were generated for the regular wave cases. A JONSWAP-type spectrum ($\gamma=3.3$) was considered for the random wave tests. A total number of 45 tests were carried out, including 20 with regular and 25 with random waves. In table 1 target wave conditions are presented.

Table 1. Target parameters for generated waves

4. Numerical model setup. Calibration and validation

In this section the computational setup is presented. The model is calibrated based on comparisons with experimental free surface time series. Next, computations are validated against the experimental data obtained in the laboratory including free surface time series, spectra and pressure time series at the caisson.

4.1 Computational domain

Following the experimental setup and previous experience on the application of the numerical model, the computational domain and the grid resolution is taken to be as shown in Figure 3. An internal wave generator, (Lara et al. 2006a) is used to generate the target incident wave characteristics included in Table 1.

Figure 3. Sketch of computational mesh resolution.

The choice of grid size varies in the y -direction from 1 cm above de SWL (region 1) to 3 cm under the SWL (region 2). In the x -direction a coarser grid size, 5 cm, is used in the generation region, increasing the resolution up to 2 cm in the vicinity of the breakwater, which is the area of interest (region 3). A total number of 92 grids is used in the y -direction, while in the x -direction 2325 grids are used. As can be seen in Figure 4, the computational domain, where the spending beach is included, is 25 meters longer than the laboratory wave flume. This is due to the fact that a sponge layer has been located in Region 1 in order to absorb the reflected energy at the structure and waves generated by the internal source function in the offshore direction. The same computational setup has been used for all the cases presented in this paper.

Other grid resolutions have been tested in order to evaluate the computational time and the accuracy of the results. Using a resolution of 0.5 cm in both the horizontal and vertical direction increases computational time in a factor of 30 with not much improvement in the accuracy of the results but better defining of the tongue of water overtopping the structure.

4.2. Model calibration and validation

As previously explained, the model solves the VARANS equations proposed by Hsu *et al.* (2002). The porous media flow in the VARANS equations is modeled by including the extended Forchheimer relationship in the momentum equations, in which both linear and nonlinear drag forces are included. The expression used in the model for the linear and nonlinear drag forces is given by,

$$I = \frac{\alpha \nu (1-n)^2}{n^2 D_{50}^2} \bar{u} + \frac{\beta (1-n)}{n^2 D_{50}} \bar{u} |\bar{u}|$$

where α and β are the only two empirical parameters used in the calibration of the numerical model, n is the porosity, ν the kinematic viscosity and \bar{u} stands for velocity. An additional parameter, c_A affecting the inertia term is included in the formulation to take into account the added mass. However, some preliminary runs have shown that results are almost insensitive to its variation. Therefore, for all the runs this parameter has been kept constant. A value of 0.34 has been set based on previous recommendations and our own experience.

The precise descriptions of the α and β coefficients are still not fully understood for oscillatory flows. They depend on several parameters such as the Reynolds number, the shape of the stones, the grade of the porous material, the permeability and of course the flow characteristics. Several researchers have suggested different values (e.g., Shih, 1990; van Gent *et al.*, 1994; van Gent, 1995; Burchart and Andersen, 1995). However, when comparing different formulations, attention has to be paid to the fact that discrepancies may exist in the expressions of the terms and that parameter values change depending on the flow conditions. Based on previous works, we have experienced (Garcia *et al.* 2004 and Lara *et al.* 2006a,b), that under oscillatory flow and waves propagating over slopes or breaking, values existing in the literature may not be valid

since the experimental conditions for obtaining those formulae were not considering these effects.

In this work the best-fit values for α and β are evaluated by comparing experimental data and numerical results of free surface and pressure time series for two regular wave cases: ra31 ($H=0.1$ m and $T=3$ s) and ra51 ($H=0.1$ m and $T=5$ s).

After a trial and error process, the best-fit parameter values calculated were $\alpha = 200$ and $\beta = 0.8$ for the breakwater core; $\alpha = 200$ and $\beta = 1.1$ for the small gravel external layer and $\alpha = 200$ and $\beta = 0.7$ for the big gravel external layer. Numerical results appeared to be more sensitive to the nonlinear drag coefficient β than the linear drag parameter α , because the flow is mainly turbulent. Once the coefficients were determined, they were kept constant for every other case considered in this work.

It is important to point out that these empirical parameters could be used as tuning parameters to obtain better adjustment between numerical calculations and experimental data. However, they remained constant for all the other numerical calculations in order to show the ability of the model to simulate the experiments with the lowest number of calibration coefficients possible.

4.3. Free surface time series

Results of free surface time series are presented in figures 4 to 6 for three different tests: a regular wave case ra35 ($H=0.25$ m and $T=5$ s); and two irregular wave cases ia66 ($H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=6$ s) and ia55 ($H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=5$ s), where H_s and T_p are the significant wave height and peak period, respectively. Results are presented for seven positions, four in front of the structure and three over the crown.

Figure 4 plots the free surface time histories from both the numerical model and experimental data for regular waves (rb35). The figure, showing 50 waves, indicates an

excellent agreement between the numerical results and the measurements for both wave phase and height, especially in front of the breakwater. Reflection patterns and waves shoaling on the slope are represented very well. The first and second wave gauges on the top of the caisson also show an excellent agreement in terms of phase, with errors in wave height close to grid size. Discrepancies in WG13 can mainly be attributed to the fact that the numerical model's grid size adopted in the simulation is too large to reproduce the phenomenon.

Figures 5 and 6 correspond to the measurements and numerical solutions for the free surface time series at 7 different positions for irregular waves, cases ib66 and ib55 with the same significant wave height and slightly different peak periods. Approximately, 50 waves are represented in each panel. As expected the irregular wave cases are more difficult to model. However, in both cases the agreement between numerical results and experimental data is very good, especially in front of the structure. The differences in WG11, WG12 and WG13 are mostly due to the difficulty in simulating isolated overtopping events, since small wave height differences in front of the structure produce significant differences in overtopping results. However, most of the overtopping events registered in WG11 have been simulated by the numerical model. In general, the model gives a slight over prediction of the number of overtopping events. Differences are certainly due to deviations in the prediction of wave height and wave sequence. For example, for case ib55, figure 6 between $t=100$ s and $t=150$ s, the model predicts very well the 4 first overtopping events recorded in WG11 and predicts a large overtopping event not measured. The analysis of the free surface evolution in WG10 shows that prior to this event, the model underpredicts the wave height in the experiments probably predicting a non existent wave breaking. In fact a small overtopping event, not predicted by the model is recorded in the experiments. This smaller predicted wave may result in a

different rundown and therefore it may modify the effect on the structure of the following wave in the time history.

Figure 4. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case rb35: $H=0.25\text{ m}$ $T=3\text{ s}$

Figure 5. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s =0.18\text{ m}$ $T_p=6\text{ s}$

Figure 6. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib55: $H_s =0.18\text{ m}$ $T_p=5\text{ s}$

4.4. Wave energy spectra

An accurate description of the spectral evolution of the wave conditions in front of the structure is essential for a correct assessment of the breakwater performance. Figure 7 presents the comparison of the experimental and numerical wave spectra at 13 different locations along the flume for case ib66. In general, the agreement between the numerical results and the experimental data is very good but for gauge 8, on the slope of the breakwater, where the model underpredicts the energy measured in the spectrum. The transformation of the wave spectrum along the flume is clearly evident for both the experimental and the numerical results. The spectral shape is generally well predicted. The energy is distributed mainly between the main harmonic which corresponds to the peak period, $f=0.166\text{ Hz}$ and a second harmonic at $f=0.333\text{ Hz}$ due to the non linear process taking place during the wave-structure interaction process.

Due to the reflection process on the structure, a partial standing system is established with nodes (WG5 and WG7) and antinodes (WG6 and WG8) along the flume. The zero moment wave height shows a very good agreement with a mean error between numerical and experimental value about 5%.

Figure 7. Free surface spectra, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18m$ $T_p = 6s$

4.5. Pressure time series

In order to conclude the validation process, pressure time series underneath and on the seaward face of the caisson are analyzed. The upper panel of Figure 8 shows the distribution of the 10 pressure gauges on the caisson. The lower panels plot comparisons between predicted and experimental pressure time series for approximately 50 waves, in case ib66. In general, the model gives a very accurate prediction of the recorded pressure time series. It is important to note that the prediction of pressure time series, especially in gauges PG3 to PG10 is very difficult since it requires an excellent simulation of the flow across the different porous layers. Gauges PG1 to PG4 in the front face of the caisson show a good agreement in phase and amplitude. Gauges PG2 to PG4 present a discontinuous record since, due to their location, they only register the pressure induced by the larger waves overtopping the structure. Regarding the gauges underneath the caisson, the damping induced by the porous material is clearly visible in both the numerical and the experimental records. But for minor discrepancies, the model is able to reproduce the measured time series very well in all the gauges. Please, note that the pressure time series in gauges 9 and 10 are of the same order of magnitude and non-zero.

Figure 8. Pressure time series, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p = 6$ s

5. Wave overtopping analysis

After model calibration and validation, in this section, the model is used to predict wave overtopping. Results obtained from the numerical model are summarized and compared with experimental results and existing wave overtopping formulations. Average overtopping discharge, percentage (probability) of overtopping waves and maximum overtopping volume per wave are considered to validate the model's capability to simulate wave overtopping.

5.1. Analysis of average overtopping discharges

The available literature is dominated by empirical formulations for the average overtopping discharge per unit length of structure, q (m^3/s per m), or for the dimensionless average discharge (Q). The average overtopping discharge depends on several parameters but is strongly dependent on breakwater geometry which limits the potential application of the formulae. However, it is very common in engineering to use these formulae out of their range of application.

Figure 9 presents the comparison between the experimental dimensionless average discharge and the predicted value based on 3 empirical formulations, Franco et al. (1994), Pedersen (1996) and Besley (1999). Among the formulations existing in the literature, these formulations correspond closely to the geometrical configuration of the experiments. Formulations have been applied based on the incident laboratory wave parameters (H_s and mean period, T_m) calculated only from the segment of the total wave

record simulated numerically. From the 25 experimental cases, only the irregular wave cases with overtopping events are included in the plot. The dimensionless average discharge per meter is plotted versus a dimensionless freeboard. Franco et al. (1994) considered several configurations including a vertical wall with and without perforated front and a composite structure setup. Based on this formula, the predicted values also overestimate the measured average discharge. However, the differences between measured and predicted values tend to be reduced with increasing dimensionless freeboard. The second formulation by Pedersen (1996) considered a rock armored permeable slope with a berm in front of a crown wall under irregular wave attacks. Overtopping average discharge obtained by Pedersen (1996) formula clearly underestimates the laboratory results. The last formulation considered, obtained by Besley (1999), is based on previous work by Bradbury and Allsop (1988) and Owen (1980) and considers rock armored permeable slopes with crown walls. In general, this formula gives the best fit to the experimental measurements. This plot is just a demonstration that, as expected, the evaluation of overtopping is highly dependent on the hydraulic model test results used to fit the semi-empirical formulae. Therefore, results are subject to structure geometry, wave steepness, wave breaking type, etc.

Figure 9. Wave overtopping dimensionless average discharge vs. dimensionless freeboard. Comparison between experimental and predicted values using semi-empirical formulae.

As said, numerical modeling of wave overtopping may be less restrictive, since it may be a complementary tool, in theory, useful to configure any structure and consider a

much larger range of cases. COBRAS-UC is being developed as such a tool. One of the main advantages of using COBRAS-UC is that it is able to provide time history of wave overtopping and therefore, gives the opportunity to analyze individual overtopping events which may be more important than the average discharge.

In order to show COBRAS-UC capability to address wave overtopping of structures, Figures 10 to 12 plot the time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and the average discharge over the simulation period shown in plot, Q_A , for a regular wave case, rb65 and two irregular wave cases, ib66 e ib55.

Figure 10. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A .

Case rb65: $H=0.25m$ $T=6s$.

For the regular wave case, Figure 10, it can be seen that even when minor differences exist, there is a very good agreement between the numerical and experimental accumulated overtopping discharge time history. The accumulated overtopping discharge increases with a constant slope. The comparison between the numerical and experimental average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot shows an excellent agreement with a 4.7 % error.

Figure 11. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case

ib66: $H_s = 0.18 m$ $T_p = 6s$

The average discharge over the simulation period increases to 8% for case ib66, Figure 11, but the agreement between the numerical and experimental results is still excellent considering the fact that overtopping by irregular waves is simulated. Regarding the time history simulation of accumulated overtopping discharge the numerical results show a very good agreement with experimental data, especially during the first 300 seconds.

Figure 12. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case

$$ib55: H_s = 0.18m \quad T_p = 5s$$

Finally, for the shorter peak period, case ib55, Figure 12, the agreement is also very good for both the time history and average accumulated discharge, proving the ability of COBRAS-UC to simulate, with a high degree of accuracy the wave overtopping process in complicated structures.

It should be noted that minor wave height differences in front of the breakwater may induce significant differences in the overtopped amount of water. Because of that, few waves incorrectly simulated fairly affect the averaged overtopping rate. As it was expected, the highest accumulated overtopping discharge corresponds to the regular wave case which doubles the accumulated overtopping volume reached after 200 second simulation for the irregular wave cases. This is due to the number of overtopping waves, which is higher for the rb65 case.

Since the dimensionless average discharge, Q , is one of the most used parameters in engineering design, Figure 13 presents the Q values predicted by COBRAS-UC versus the experimental values for the 18 cases tested in the laboratory including wave

overtopping events. As can be seen, the model gives a good agreement showing a small general trend to underestimate the experimental results.

Figure 13. Dimensionless average discharge. Comparison between numerical and experimental values for all the tested cases including overtopping

Finally, Figure 14 shows the comparison between the average overtopping discharges obtained using COBRAS-UC, the semi-empirical formulae previously presented and the experimental values.

The plot shows that the best agreement between numerical and experimental results is obtained by COBRAS-UC. The mean error of the numerical model is -9% with a standard deviation of $\pm 41.8\%$. Besley (1999) shows a mean error of +87% and a standard deviation of 100%. Franco et al. (1994) shows a better performance with a mean error of +45% and a standard deviation of $\pm 92\%$. Although Besley (1999) includes the effect of the rock slope roughness and the influence of the rock berm width, Franco et al. (1994) gives the closest fit to the experimental results among the formulae.

Figure 14. Average wave overtopping discharge – Comparison between semi-empirical formulae, model and laboratory.

5.2. Percentage of overtopping waves and probability distribution of overtopping volumes per wave

The model has shown a good agreement for the most used overtopping parameter, the average overtopping discharge. However, there are other parameters that have been

introduced in literature to represent such a complex phenomenon. In nature, overtopping events present a random distribution both in time and amount and usually a small number of waves control the main part of overtopped amount of water. Many authors have tried to represent this process by plotting measured overtopping volumes in a probability paper. According to Franco et al. (1994) and Franco and Franco (1999) the exceedance probability of each overtopping volume $P(V)$ can be calculated with a three-parameter Weibull distribution function, which is found to give a good statistical description of the data. This probability can be expressed in terms of 3 fitting coefficients A, B and C, which are the scale, shape and set-off fitting coefficients, respectively. The set-off coefficient C, represents the percentage (probability) of overtopping waves (N_{ow}/N_w), where N_{ow} and N_w are the number of overtopping waves and number of incident waves, respectively. Assuming the percentage of overtopping waves to be Rayleigh distributed, Franco et al. (1994) defines the following expression for C,

$$C = \frac{N_{ow}}{N_w} = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{1}{k} \frac{R_c}{H_s}\right)^2\right)$$

were, k is a best fitting constant recommended to be 0.91 for caisson breakwaters.

Figure 15 shows the comparison between probability of overtopping, represented by the set-off coefficient, C, observed in the laboratory versus the values predicted by the model and the formulation by Franco et al. (1994). The numerical results show a very good agreement as was expected, because the average overtopping discharges were very well simulated. Cases with probability of overtopping close to one correspond to highly energetic regular waves where every single wave overtops the structure. Cases with probability close to zero are irregular and regular cases with low wave height; therefore no overtopping events exist..

Figure 15. Set-off coefficient $C=(N_{ow}/N_w)$ representing the percentage of overtopping wave. Comparison between numerical, semi-empirical and observed values.

Works like Franco et al. (1994) show that the maximum overtopping volume is also a very important parameter to be studied. The accumulated overtopping volume is usually dominated by only a few overtopping events. The numerical model is a suitable tool to predict the instantaneous discharge and therefore the maximum overtopping event.

The measured and computed maximum discharge volumes are compared in Figure 16 with the numerical and measured volume for the irregular and regular waves. In general, the numerical results show a very good agreement for all regular wave cases. However, the model tends to give a slight over- or underestimation of the maximum volume for some irregular cases. The underestimation is due probably to the lack of agreement in some waves of the record which highly affects to the maximum discharge. COBRAS-UC shows a mean error of -8% with a standard deviation of $\pm 46\%$.

Figure 16. Comparison between experimental, numerical and semi-empirical results for maximum overtopping volume, V_{max}

6. Concluding remarks

By improving several aspects of the initial version of the COBRAS model, COBRAS-UC allows the application of a numerical model solving the volume-average RANS equations and corresponding k- ϵ equations, to the investigation of wave overtopping on

a rubble mound breakwater built of permeable layers made of different materials. The improvements in this new version allow for longer computational times that can vary from hundreds to thousands of waves depending on the grid resolution and the processes to be considered, in reasonable periods of time and on standard PCs. Based on the numerical simulation of a detailed experimental set of experiments carried out with regular and irregular waves, it can be concluded that the present version of the model is capable of predicting the free surface in front of the structure as well as on the top of the impermeable caisson very well. Furthermore, the pressure time series on the front face and, especially underneath the caisson are very well predicted, suggesting that the modeling of porous flow is correct. From the analysis of wave overtopping, and based on the excellent results achieved comparing average overtopping discharge and other overtopping parameters, it can be concluded that COBRAS-UC has an excellent potential to become a complementary tool to existing semi-empirical formulations and may be used to predict wave overtopping, extending the range of incident wave conditions or breakwater geometries considered in the experimental setup.

Even though the model has performed very well, there is still room for further investigations and improvements. The computational efficiency of the model must be upgraded. Results presented in this paper have been calculated with a 1 cm resolution in the vertical direction and a 2 cm resolution in the horizontal direction in the area of interest which is a valid resolution for a setup at this scale if overtopping is the main interest. All the simulations have been performed with 200-400 waves with maximum computational times of 30 hours on a standard PC. However, it must be said that a reduction in grid resolution, results in a considerable speed up of the computation but a worse performance in terms of overtopping. Therefore, to be competitive with NSWE

models in terms of computation, the code has to be upgraded to run 1000 waves in reasonable periods of time.

A second issue to be considered is a detailed analysis of the dependency of the empirical coefficients, α and β , associated with the linear and nonlinear drag force in the porous media flow. There is still a strong dependency on the flow that could be parameterized partially with the Reynolds number that needs to be solved.

Finally, including the effect of air on the wave and structure interaction process could also be of interest for the analysis of some specific situations.

Acknowledgments

The authors are indebted to Puertos del Estado (State Ports of Spain) for the funding provided to carry out this research.

References

- Allsop, N. W., Hawkes, P. I., Jackson, F.A., and Franco, L., 1985. Wave Run-Up on Steep Slopes – Model Tests Under Random Waves. Report No. SR2, Hydraulics Research Station, Wallingford, England.
- Besley, P, 1999. Overtopping of seawalls: design and assessment manual. Environment Agency. Bristol, R&D Technical Report No.W178, 1999, 37 pp CEM, Coastal Engineering Manual.
- Bradbury, A. P., and Allsop, N. W. 1988. “A Hydraulic Effects of Breakwater Crown Walls”, Proceedings of the Breakwaters '88 Conference, Institution of Civil Engineers, Thomas Telford Publishing, London, UK, pp 385-396.

Burcharth, H.F., Andersen, O.H. 1995. On the one-dimensional steady and unsteady porous flow equations. *Coastal Engineering*, 24: 233-257.

Dalrymple, R.A., Knio, O., Cox, D.T., Gomez-Gesteira, M., Zou, S., 2001. Using a Lagrangian particle method for deck overtopping. *Proc. Waves ASCE 2001*, pp. 1082–1091.

Franco, C., and Franco, L., 1999. Overtopping Formulas for Caisson Breakwaters with nonbreaking 3D Waves. *Journal of Waterway, Port, Coastal, and Ocean Engineering*, American Society of Civil Engineers, Vol 125, No. 2, pp 98-108.

Franco, L., de Gerloni, M., van der Meer, J.W., 1994. Wave Overtopping on Vertical and composite Breakwaters. *Proceedings of the 24th International Coastal Engineering Conference*, American Society of Civil Engineers, Vol 1, pp 1030-1045.

Garcia, N., Lara, J.L., Losada, I.J., 2004. 2-D Numerical analysis of near-field flow at low-crested permeable breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering*, 51, 991-1020.

Gotoh, H., Shao, S.D., Memita, T., 2004. SPH–LES model for numerical investigation of wave interaction with partially immersed breakwater. *Coastal Engineering of Japan*. 46 (1), 39–63.

Hedges T. S., and M. T. Reis (1998). A Random wave overtopping of simple sea walls. A new regression model. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers. Water Maritime and Energy*.

Owen M W. “Design of seawalls allowing for wave overtopping”. HR Wallingford, Report EX 924, 1980.

Hsu, T.-J., Sakakiyama, T., Liu, P.L.-F., 2002. A numerical model for wave motions and turbulence flows in front of a composite breakwater. *Coastal Engineering*, 46, 25-50.

Hu, K., Mingham, C.G., Causon, D.M., 2000. Numerical simulation of wave overtopping of coastal structures using the non-linear shallow water equations. *Coast. Eng.* 41, 433–465.

Hubbard, M.E., Dodd, N. 2002 A 2D numerical model of wave run-up and overtopping. *Coastal Engineering*, vol. 47, pp. 1-26.

Kawasaki, K., 1999. Numerical simulation of breaking and post-breaking wave deformation process around a submerged breakwater. *Coastal Engineering Journal*, 41: 201-223.

Kobayashi, N., Wurjanto, A., 1989. Wave transmission over submerged breakwaters. *Journal of Waterways, Port, Coastal and Ocean Engineering*, 115: 662-680.

- Kobayashi, N., Wurjanto, A., 1989. Wave overtopping on coastal structures. *J. Waterw., Port, Coast., Ocean Eng., ASCE* 115, 235–251.
- Kothe, D.B., Mjølness, R.C., Torrey, M.D., 1991. RIPPLE: a computer program for incompressible flows with free surface. Los Alamos National Laboratory, LA-12007-MS.
- Koshizuka, S., Tamako, H., Oka, Y., 1995. A particle method for incompressible viscous flow with fluid fragmentation. *Comput. Fluid Dyn. J.* 4 (1), 29–46.
- Lara, J.L., Garcia, N. and Losada, I.J., 2006a. RANS modelling applied to random wave interaction with submerged permeable structures. *Coastal Engineering*, 53, 395-417.
- Lara, J.L., Losada, I.J., Liu, P.L.-F. 2006b. Breaking waves over a mild gravel slope: experimental and numerical analysis. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, AGU, Vol. 111, C11019; doi: 10-1029/2005 JC003374.
- Li, T., Troch, P., De Rouck, J., 2004. Wave overtopping over a sea dike, *Journal of Computational Physics*. 198, 686-726.
- Li, T.Q., Troch, P., Rouck, J.D., 2004. Wave overtopping over a sea dike. *J. Comp. Physics*. 198, 686–726.
- Lin, P.Z., Liu, P.L.F., 1998. A numerical study of breaking waves in the surf zone. *J. Fluid Mech.* 359, 239–264.
- Liu, P.L.F., Lin, P.Z., Chang, K.A., Sakakiyama, T., 1999. Numerical modelling of wave interaction with porous structures. *J. Waterw., Port, Coast., Ocean Eng., ASCE* 125 (6), 322–330.
- Losada, I.J., 2003. Advances in modeling the effects of permeable and reflective structures on waves and nearshore flows. In: *Advances in Coastal Modeling*. Elsevier Oceanography Series, Vol. 67. Ed. V. Chris Lakhan.
- Losada, I.J., 2005. Advances in the design and construction of coastal structures. Chapter 3, In: *Port and Coastal Engineering*. Ed. P. Bruun. Coastal Engineering Research Foundation. ISBN 1891276506. pp. 55-99.

- Losada, I.J., Lara, J.L., Damgaard, E., Garcia, N., 2005. Modelling of velocity and turbulence fields around and within low-crested rubble-mound breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering*, 52, 887-913.
- Mingham, C.G., Causon, D.M., 1998. High-resolution finite-volume method for shallow water flows. *J. Hydraul. Eng.*, ASCE 124 (6), 605–614.
- Pedersen, J., 1996. Experimental Study of Wave Forces and Wave Overtopping on Breakwater Crown Walls,” Series paper 12, Hydraulics & Coastal Engineering Laboratory, Department of Civil Engineering, Aalborg University, Denmark.
- Shao, S., Ji, C., Graham, D.I., Reeve, D.E., James, P.W., Chadwick, A.J., 2006. Simulation of wave overtopping by an incompressible SPH model. *Coastal Engineering*, 53, 723-735.
- Stansby, P.K., Feng, T., 2004. Surf zone wave overtopping a trapezoidal structure: 1-D modelling and PIV comparison. *Coast. Eng.* 51, 483–500.
- Troch, P., de Rouck, J., 1998. Development of two-dimensional numerical wave flume for wave interaction with rubble mound breakwaters. 26th Int. Coastal Eng. Conf., pp. 1638-1649.
- Van der Meer, J.W., Janssen, J.P.F.M., 1995. Wave run-up and wave overtopping at dikes. *Wave Forces on Inclined and Vertical Structures ASCE – Task Committee Reports*, pp. 1–27.
- Van Gent, M.R.A., 1995. “Wave interaction with permeable coastal structures”. Ph.D. Thesis, Delft University Press.

List of Figures

Figure 1. Breakwater geometry (dimension in meters)

Figure 2. Instrumentation set-up. Pressure gauges (PG) and free surface gauges (WG).

Figure 3. Sketch of computational mesh resolution.

Figure 4. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case rb35: $H=0.25$ m $T=3$ s

Figure 5. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p=6$ s

Figure 6. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib55: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p=5$ s

Figure 7. Free surface spectra, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p=6$ s

Figure 8. Pressures time series, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p=6$ s

Figure 9. Wave overtopping dimensionless average discharge vs. dimensionless freeboard. Comparison between experimental and predicted values using semi-empirical formulae.

Figure 10. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case rb65: $H=0.25$ m $T=6$ s.

Figure 11. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p=6$ s

Figure 12. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case ib55: $H_s = 0.18\text{m}$ $T_p = 5\text{s}$

Figure 13. Dimensionless average discharge. Comparison between numerical and experimental values for all the tested cases including overtopping

Figure 14. Average wave overtopping discharge – Comparison between semi-empirical formulae, model and laboratory.

Figure 15. Set-off coefficient $C = (N_{ow}/N_w)$ representing the percentage of overtopping wave. Comparison between numerical, semi-empirical and observed values.

Figure 16. Comparison between experimental, numerical and semi-empirical results for maximum overtopping volume, V_{max}

List of Tables

Table 1. Target parameters for generated waves

Figure 1. Breakwater geometry (dimension in meters)

Figure 2. Instrumentation set-up. Pressure gauges (PG) and free surface gauges (WG).

Figure 3. Sketch of computational mesh resolution.

Figure 4. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case rb35: $H=0.25$ m $T=3$ s

Figure 5. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18$ m $T_p = 6$ s

Figure 6. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib55: $H_s = 0.18\text{m}$ $T_p = 5\text{s}$

Figure 7. Free surface spectra, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line:

numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s = 0.18\text{m}$ $T_p = 6\text{s}$

Figure 8. Pressures time evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ib66: $H_s=0.18$ m $T_p=6$ s

Figure 9. Wave overtopping dimensionless average discharge vs. dimensionless freeboard. Comparison between experimental and predicted values using semi-empirical formulae.

Figure 10. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case

rb65: $H=0.25\text{m}$ $T=6\text{s}$.

Figure 11. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case

ib66: $H_s = 0.18 \text{ m}$ $T_p = 6\text{s}$

Figure 12. Experimental and numerical time history of the accumulated overtopping discharge and average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plot, Q_A . Case

ib55: $H_s = 0.18\text{m}$ $T_p = 5\text{s}$

Figure 13. Dimensionless average discharge. Comparison between numerical and experimental values for all the tested cases including overtopping

Figure 14. Average wave overtopping discharge – Comparison between semi-empirical formulae, model and laboratory.

Figure 15. Set-off coefficient $C=(N_{ow}/N_w)$ representing the percentage of overtopping wave. Comparison between numerical, semi-empirical and observed values.

Figure 16. Comparison between experimental and numerical results for maximum overtopping volume, V_{\max}

Wave type		Regular		Irregular
Wave height	H(m)	0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.225,0.25	H _s (m)	0.084, 0.12, 0.15, 0.18, 0.21
Wave period	T(s)	2, 3, 4, 5, 6	T _p (s)	2, 3, 4, 5, 6
Water depth at wave paddle	h(m)	0.8	h(m)	0.8
Water length at wave paddle	L(m)	4.89 to 16.56	L(m)	4.89 to 16.56
Wave steepness	H/L	0.00604 to 0.0511	H _s /L	0.005724 to 0.0429
Relative freeboard	F/H	0.8 to 2	F/H _s	0.95 to 2.38
Relative crest width	B/L	0.0604 to 0.204	B/L	0.0604 to 0.204
Relative wave height	H/h	0.125 to 0.3125	H _s /h	0.104 to 0.2625
Relative depth	h/L	0.0483 to 0.1636	h/L	0.0483 to 0.1636

Table 1. Target parameters for generated waves